

Study of the Cross Section of the $^{133}\text{Cs}(p,3n)^{131}\text{Ba}$ Reaction for the Production of the Medical Isotope ^{131}Ba

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Abstract

Radioisotopes play an important role in many nuclear medicine applications such as cancer diagnosis, research, monitoring and treatment of other biological phenomena. Barium-131 has a suitable half-life of 11.5 days for medical use and is a radioisotope compatible with Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT) for nuclear medicine. Due to the similar chemistry and pharmacological properties of the elements barium and radium, barium-131 can be used diagnostically with the therapeutic alpha emitters radium-223 and radium-224. It is therefore expected that the radioisotope barium-131 will be used in the future as part of current approaches to the treatment of bone cancer and bone metastases. The cross sections of the $^{133}\text{Cs}(p,3n)^{131}\text{Ba}$ reaction producing barium-131 are calculated for different nuclear parameters and compared with available experimental results.

1. Introduction

Radioisotopes employed in the field of medicine can be generated through the utilization of nuclear reactors, particle accelerators and radioisotope generators [1, 2]. Radioisotopes play a significant role in numerous nuclear medicine applications, including cancer diagnosis, research, monitoring, and treatment of other biological processes. Low-dose radioisotopes that emit short-lived beta plus and gamma rays are employed in imaging techniques such as positron emission tomography (PET) and single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) [3]. Radioisotopes that emit relatively long-lived but short-range high-ionizing radiation are utilized for treatment purposes. Additionally, there are radioisotopes that are employed for both diagnostic and therapeutic applications [5].

In the early 1970s, extensive research was conducted into the potential use of barium-131 as a bone-targeting agent [3, 4]. Barium-131 has a favorable half-life of 11.5 days, which makes it suitable for medical use. Furthermore, it is a radioisotope compatible with single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) for nuclear medicine [5]. Given the analogous chemistry and pharmacological characteristics of barium and radium, barium-131 is particularly well-suited for diagnostic applications in conjunction with the therapeutic alpha emitters radium-223 and radium-224 [3, 4].

The calcimimetic behavior of free barium ions renders barium-131 a valuable long-term bone-targeting radioisotope. It is anticipated that the radioisotope barium-131 will be employed in the future as part of the current approaches to the treatment of bone cancer and bone metastases [3, 5].

In nuclear reactors, ^{131}Ba can be produced by the (n,γ) reaction of the stable isotope ^{130}Ba through neutron bombardment [2]. However, given the low natural abundance of barium-130 (0.11%), the use of an enriched ^{130}Ba target is necessary to achieve the requisite levels of ^{131}Ba production [4]. Additionally, ^{131}Ba can be produced through the utilization of particle accelerators [4]. The production of ^{133}Cs can be achieved through the $^{133}\text{Cs}(p,3n)^{131}\text{Ba}$ reaction, whereby the target is bombarded with protons of an appropriate energy in a particle accelerator. Given that there is only one stable isotope of natural cesium (^{133}Cs), the use of an enriched isotope is unnecessary. Barium-131 ($t_{1/2} = 11.5$ d) decays via cesium-131 ($t_{1/2} = 9.7$ d) to stable xenon-131, in each case by electron capture (Figure 1). In particular, the γ -ray emitted during the first decay with an energy of 123.8 keV (30%) is well suited for single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) imaging [3, 5].

In this study, the cross sections of the $^{133}\text{Cs}(p,3n)^{131}\text{Ba}$ reaction (Figure 2), which is a pivotal parameter for the production of medical barium-131, have been calculated for different nuclear parameters and compared with the available experimental results.

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Figure 1. Illustrates the decay path of barium-131, along with the energies and intensities of the gamma rays emitted.

2. Materials and Methods

In order to analyze the production of medical barium isotopes, it is essential to possess a comprehensive understanding of the reaction cross-section values across a broad energy spectrum. It is regrettable that there is a paucity of experimental studies encompassing a broad energy range with minimal uncertainty. Accordingly, there is a requirement for the undertaking of theoretical calculations of the reaction cross-section at energies that fall outside the scope of the available experimental data.

The latest version of the TALYS code will be employed for cross-section calculations. TALYS is a robust tool for modelling and analyzing nuclear reactions in nuclear physics and nuclear engineering [6]. Parameters such as nuclear potential, energy level density and gamma force function are utilized in the theoretical cross-section calculation. In this study, reaction cross-sections are calculated in accordance with different optical models (Table 2).

Table 1. Properties of the radiation emitted from the production of medical barium-131 isotopes by the $^{131}\text{Cs}(p,3n)^{131}\text{Ba}$ reaction and from the second decay product.

Isotope (Half life)	Production and Decay Mode	Radiation Type	E γ (keV)	I γ (%)
^{131}Ba (11.50 d)	$^{131}\text{Cs}(p,3n)^{131}\text{Ba}$	Auger L	3.55	105.8
		γ	496.32	48.0
		γ	4.29	12.3
		γ	30.63	28.0
		γ	30.97	51.2
		γ	34.92	4.85
		γ	34.99	9.35
^{131}Cs (9.689 h)	Decay of ^{131}Ba	Auger K	24.6	9.3
		γ	29.46	21.1
		γ	29.78	38.9
		γ	33.56	3.64
		γ	33.62	7.02
		γ	35.82	2.90

Figure 2. Barium-131 production route by $^{133}\text{Cs}(p,3n)^{131}\text{Ba}$ reaction in accelerators.

Table 2. Outlines the microscopic and phenomenological optical potentials employed in cross-section calculations [6].

OMP No	Optical Model Potentials
0	standard JLM imaginary potential
1	0.44 replaced by $1.1e^{(-0.4E^{1/2})}$
2	0.44 replaced by $1.25e^{(-0.2E^{1/2})}$
3	as 2 but with $\lambda W(E)$ twice as large, recommended for energies below 1 MeV.
4	phenomenological optical model potential

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 3 shows the calculated cross sections with different optical model potentials and experimental cross section measurements found in the literature. With the exception of the optical model, all other parameters were set to their default values as defined by the TALYS code. The calculations were performed in the energy range of 19 to 70 MeV, with increments of 0.1 MeV.

From the results of the different optical model calculations, it can be observed that the maximum value of the cross-section is reached at approximately 28 MeV (Figure 3). The difference between the theoretical and experimental cross sections is greatest in the region of maximum cross section. All the theoretical calculations give results that are close to each other but not in good agreement with the experimental data.

Figure 3. Comparison of cross section calculations with different optical potential models and experimental results.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the cross sections of the $^{133}\text{Cs}(p,3n)^{131}\text{Ba}$ reaction, which is a crucial parameter for the production of medical barium-131, were calculated with different nuclear optical potential models and compared with the available experimental results.

No consensus was reached between the theoretical calculations and the experimental results at any of the energies for which calculations were performed. In addition to the nuclear optical potentials, the energy level density and gamma strength function models contribute to the cross section calculations. Therefore, it is necessary to perform separate calculations with all available models [7, 8].

It should also be noted that the experimental measurements in the literature were conducted using thick targets, and errors in energy measurements are a possibility. Therefore, it is essential to further reduce the uncertainties in both energy and cross section in experimental measurements for this reaction [9, 10].

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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